

Concatenative Synthesis Unit Navigation and Dynamic Rearrangement in *vrGrains*

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ABSTRACT

Corpus based concatenative synthesis has been approached from different perspectives by many researchers. This generated a number of diverse solutions addressing the matter of target selection, corpus visualization and navigation. With this paper we introduce the concept of extended descriptor space, which permits arbitrary redistributions of audio units in space, without affecting each unit's sonic content. This feature can be exploited in novel instruments and music applications to achieve spatial dispositions which could enhance control and expression. Making use of Virtual Reality technology, we developed *vrGrains*, an immersive installation in which real-time corpus navigation is based on the concept of extended descriptor space and on the related audio unit rearrangement capabilities. The user is free to explore a corpus represented by 3D units which physically surrounds her/him. Through natural interaction, the interface provides different interaction modalities which allow controllable and chaotic audio unit triggering and motion.

1. INTRODUCTION

The possibility to explore sounds in domains different from the temporal one is a fascinating concept. Throughout real-time corpus-based concatenative synthesis (CBCS) [1], audio segments (called *units*) can be re-synthesized, breaking their rigid time order and following instead arbitrary paths in a multi-dimensional space, defined by a set of sound descriptors. From this perspective, each unit is not characterized by its position in time, it intrinsically carries the information resulting from descriptor analysis (e.g., *loudness*, *pitch*, *periodicity*) and, according to these values, it occupies a specific position within the current descriptor space. Previous works have mostly focused on navigating in the descriptor space. Proposed solutions differ in methods for target selection and corpus visualization, but they always share the use of domains where units occupy a fixed position. For example, the choice of a mono-dimensional domain defined by loudness produces a corpus scattering that could be modified only through a direct gain alteration

for each unit. Then, this process must be followed by a further descriptor analysis on the modified corpus, to update visualized data. Since used corpora often produce uneven scattering within the descriptor space [2–4], the inability to quickly change unit positions without affecting their sonic characteristics could limit usability and expression.

With this paper we present *vrGrains*, a Virtual Reality (VR) audio/visual installation characterized by an innovative technique for corpus navigation, based on the concept of extended descriptor space. In contrast to solutions featured in previous works, in *vrGrains* audio units are distributed within a three-dimensional physical space which is not strictly coupled with high and low level sound descriptors. The user is free to move all the units around the space, to achieve spatial dispositions which could enhance synthesis expression during exploration. This process produces continuous changes of physical descriptor values (i.e., the ones which determine unit positions), without interfering with each unit's sonic content. Furthermore, the user is allowed to temporally link the (x, y, z) physical values to chosen sound descriptors, to suddenly rearrange the corpus scattering according to its sonic properties. By means of VR technology, we included these features into an immersive installation for soundscape exploration. The user is completely immersed within the corpus, she/he can move inside of it, and have direct access to the stereoscopic representations of each unit through natural interaction. The result is a dynamic navigation throughout the corpus, during which the distribution of units within the space can be modified, even randomized, applying forces and generating collisions. It can then be reverted to its original arrangement, according to user control.

2. RELATED WORK

A large number of research projects show different possible approaches to real-time CBCS [1]. Many of these projects involve the use of D. Schwarz's CataRT [3] to implement corpus navigation and audio synthesis.

CataRT's integrated explorative interface (CataRT *lcd*) allows the exploration of a bi-dimensional projection of the descriptor space, where units are represented as small colored dots. Its navigation, and thus the sound unit triggering, is based on mouse cursor movements around the corpus, combined with different available triggering modalities. Additional external controls can be used to explore descriptors other than the ones available on the 2D interface. This fea-

ture allows navigation of the descriptor spaces which have more than 2 dimensions, but always with fixed units scattering. Furthermore, when dimensionality is higher than 2, the application does not provide a visual representation of the space.

Plumage [5] is a CataRT based project, structured around the visualization of corpus sound units within a 3D environment. It works as direct extension of the CataRT *lcd*. As in *vrGrains*, the user can move a selector (called *reading head*) in the descriptor space, triggering units according to a 3 dimensional distance criterion. To overcome the common problem of uneven corpus scattering and to ensure a continuous audio output during exploration, the number of reading heads per user has been increased with respect to the single built-in CataRT selector, and each head has been extended with 3D orbiting triggers.

GAVIP [6] is a VR installation in which the concept of physical modeling is applied to corpus navigation in CataRT. A number of physically modeled particles move within a 3D virtual space, triggering sounds disposed in a related descriptor space, defined by *loudness* and *spectral centroid*. Sound unit selection is based on a neighborhood radius criterion, so that each moving particle can trigger the playback of nearby audio segments. GAVIP does not include any visualization of units in the virtual space, rather it focuses on audio-video-spatial *inter-modal coherency* [7]. The platform is also conceived to allow the future introduction of gesture controls influencing the particles physical behavior.

Some CBCS platforms provide the user with the possibility of interactive mosaicing. With an audio mosaic described as “the concatenation of segments of sound”, this audio synthesis technique can be defined as “a mosaicing scheme that provides a user with real-time control over the content of the mosaic” [8].

With Nuvolet [4], Comajuncosas et al. present a multi-user CataRT extension which supports both descriptor space navigation and interactive mosaicing in a 3 dimensional space. This physical space is captured by an IR device and directly mapped onto a sound space, defined by 3 descriptors. Navigation and target driven sound mosaicing are done by tracking performers’ hand movements around physical/descriptor space. This pushes corpus exploration towards a more natural interaction approach. However, a lack of precise visual feedback for the user is still present, since the sound cloud is shown to performers as a 3D overlay on a 2D monitoring screen. As previously introduced in Section 1, navigation within a sparse descriptor space is difficult; adding a third dimension without additional cognitive clues makes unit exploration even more complicated. Also, the lack of haptic feedback, typical of open-air controllers, would demand the presence of some other reliable channels [9], such as visual or kinesthetic feedbacks.

vrGrains user interface is based on natural interaction. This concept is not new and lately recurring. Natural interfaces and gestures are more and more used to interact with machines and virtual worlds (e.g., Nintendo Wii¹ and Microsoft Kinect² games) and research is pushing away

from the use of cumbersome devices [10] and increase the realism, involvement and interaction levels [11], especially inside VR applications.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

3.1 Equipment

vrGrains consists of a stereoscopic interactive environment which has continuous access to data and to synthesis algorithms of a customized Max/MSP CataRT patch, outputting a stereo audio signal.

The virtual environment is displayed onto a $4.4 \times 2 \text{ m}^2$ Powerwall³ by means of two projectors, synchronized with shutter glasses. An inertial/ultrasonic tracking system is used to detect the user’s head position and consequently modify the rendered scene perspective. User’s gesture during virtual interaction are detected through a set of 12 IR cameras for motion capture which track reflective passive markers.

Unity⁴ has been chosen as the central software, to handle graphics, scene behavior and input/output data sending. It is connected to CataRT through a bidirectional OSC connection, and it receives motion capture and head tracking data through, respectively, a UDP and a VRPN client/server setup. Active stereo visualization is handled by MiddleVR⁵, a plugin which permits Unity to have access to quad-buffer rendering capabilities.

3.2 Extended Descriptor Space

Inside the Max patch, the usual list of CataRT descriptors has been extended with three additional entries, which will represent the physical positions (expressed in floating point notation) of each unit inside the virtual environment. They are all initialized to zero (i.e., the center of the virtual environment), and set as active descriptors in the CataRT selection algorithm. At the startup, among the list of CataRT sound descriptors, three have to be chosen to create a link with the physical position of units in space. The Max patch allows the user to import a new corpus, or to extend the current corpus with units coming from sound files and/or audio input analysis. When this happens, unit data referring to the three chosen descriptors are sent to the VR application, running in Unity. Here, the data are stored, and converted into (x, y, z) positions normalizing their values according to the physical space available in front of the screen - i.e., the area in which the user is able to reach the units for direct interaction, about $4 \times 1.5 \times 2 \text{ m}^3$. For example, linking the x position descriptor to the *pitch* sound descriptor, audio units will be sorted in space on x axis according to an ascending pitch. In particular, the highest and the lowest pitched units will be positioned at the extreme x ends of the available area, respectively 2 m and -2 m . From now on, at every frame Unity accesses the CataRT data structure to overwrite the three physical descriptors values of all unit data, following the movements induced by user interaction. In this way, the units physical positions are identically

¹ <http://wii.com/>

² www.xbox.com/kinect

³ large high-resolution display wall

⁴ <http://unity3d.com>

⁵ <http://www.imin-vr.com>

mapped onto both the virtual environment in Unity and the “abstract” descriptor space in CataRT (Figure 1). This is “abstract” since it is locally represented only in a numerical form. The connection between these two different representations of the same space is expressed as multimodal feedback whenever the user triggers units, according to the various modalities that will be explained in Section 4.2.

Figure 1. System architecture for extended descriptor space. CataRT components are represented inside the Max/MSP block.

4. SOUND NAVIGATION

4.1 Tracking and Indexing

The decision to improve corpus navigation by adding a deep feel of immersion and freedom led us to implement an interface based on a natural interaction paradigm. As seen in previous research, the involvement and fun factors of VR environments are increased by the naturalness of interaction, even if in some applications this may decrease interface efficiency levels [11].

We wanted the user to move freely and spontaneously around the descriptor space using his/her hands. With a finger, the user can touch physically responsive sound units and reach specific poses with the other hand to trigger different behaviors for the sound units.

Optical motion capture represents a functional and non-invasive technique for natural interaction achievement. Only small passive reflective markers are needed for tracking body parts, avoiding the use of cumbersome devices, controllers and GUIs. Markers are lightweight and quick to place over the body thanks to adjustable velcro strips. For this installation, we decided to choose a setup similar to the one seen in [12] to track left hand thumb, index and middle fingers, plus tracking a separate marker for the right hand index finger. We also wanted to identify each left hand finger in real-time to improve pose recognition. A known issue with the tracking of unconstrained moving features is the lack of real-time distinction and association in time between the features themselves. This is an already addressed issue [13, 14] which likely benefits from application specific approaches.

For that reason, we decided to design and implement an algorithm capable of maintaining correct real-time index-

ing of free markers. Marker coordinates are periodically elaborated by two instructions sets. The first one indexes any specified number of points. This is done by storing and keeping markers univocal references based on marker interdistance over time. Also markers visibility status is stored and used to know if a marker is currently visible by the system or occluded. The variety of possible markers movements and contexts may sometimes lead the main algorithm to false correspondence detections and wrong associations. This is why a secondary algorithm has been implemented. The user can choose a reference pose which is recorded at the beginning of the tracking session. Whenever markers reach this known configuration the system forces the current indexing to match the reference one. This works as a real-time voluntary indexing correction. The initial calibration is almost instantaneous and its duration can be arbitrarily chosen.

The application of the indexing algorithm to our setup added the possibility to distinguish the fingers of the left hand in real-time. This made real-time univocal pose detection available for our project.

Optical tracking is to be considered as a choice among available systems. Being *vrGrains* an installation, an alternative and more transportable setup could be designed. Devices as Nintendo Wii Remote or Microsoft Kinect could be both used, together or separately, to explore the installation environment. The naturalness and precision given by optical tracking would be thus sacrificed in favor of a shorter setup time and a potentially greater interaction efficiency given by the presence of physical buttons.

4.2 Virtual Environment

In *vrGrains*, the user is able to explore a sound corpus inside a virtual environment. In the first instance, the installation is meant to transform corpus navigation into a strict physical experience, placing the user right inside a virtual cloud of sound segments. This is the main reason for the choice of a VR setup. The user, whose head is tracked, is free to move around the interaction area, walking from cluster to cluster, triggering and moving units. With respect to 2D environment visualization, the usage of head tracking and stereoscopy assures a certain ease of navigation within a three descriptor space, based on strong and realistic visual cues. A picture of a user inside *vrGrains* is shown in Figure 2. For a better understanding of the feeling of immersion, all the pictures included in this paper are taken placing the head tracker on the still camera, and disabling the stereoscopic effect.

Units generated from the analysis of sound files and/or audio input are represented as floating spheres which populate an empty space. Such a simple shape has been chosen as the direct 3D evolution of CataRT dots. Each sphere is characterized by a color. The RGB components of this color are assigned according to the current unit values of the three sound descriptors previously chosen for the spatial disposition. In this way, a quick visual correlation is achieved between spatial position and sphere color, highlighting the related sonic features. In addition to the three sound descriptors which link physical space to sound space,

Figure 2. A user exploring an uneven scattered corpus inside vrGrains.

the user has to select a fourth descriptor which will affect the size of each sphere and, consequently, its mass. This visual information plays a particularly important role during user interaction.

4.3 User Interaction

While moving around the virtual space, the user has a small virtual sphere attached to her/his right hand index finger. The sphere is surrounded by a transparent globular field. The sphere represents the position of the fingertip within the virtual environment. It has fixed size and mass, and it permits a physical change in the position of the units (i.e., the associated spheres). Through a direct touch, the user can generate impacts and apply changes of speed and acceleration onto the units, triggering consequent collisions against other units nearby. An invisible bounding box prevents units to move out of the interaction area.

Collision is the first triggering paradigm, since, every time two or more spheres collide, the related units are triggered in CataRT. The second triggering paradigm is based on proximity. The transparent field around the fingertip works as 3D selection radius in CataRT. Spheres inside that area are randomly chosen according to the current CataRT patch triggering mode (e.g., *bow*, *fence*, *beat*). The patch handles the two different triggering paradigms (i.e., collision and proximity) on two separate parallel synthesis engines, to allow polyphonic output.

Assuming specific poses with the left hand, the user affects the way that she/he can interact with the spheres. They have been chosen after a set of empirical tests to enable, disable and combine different interaction modalities in a natural way. Each interaction modality is characterized by a visual effect, which works as feedback to control the interaction parameters. Once reaching a pointing pose, with just index finger stretched, the user is able to change the radius of the globular field, moving closer to or further from the right hand, shrinking or enlarging the selection area. To suddenly set the radius to zero, the user has to close left hand into a fist, with the back of the hand upwards. In this way, only the unit with minimal distance from right finger is selected. During zero radius selection, the virtual environment is enriched with a red bolt which connects user's right index

finger and the currently selected sphere. With the same fist pose, but holding the back of the hand perpendicular to the ground, the spheres which are the closest to the right hand start orbiting around the right finger, triggering collisions inside the unit cloud. While moving, the orbiting spheres are connected to the user's right hand finger through blue bolts (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Blue bolts spring from user's finger to connect the orbiting spheres.

The "L" pose, with thumb and index stretched, is used to create an attractive field around the right hand. The more the left hand moves far from the right one, the bigger the radius of this green field grows (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Here the user is enlarging the green field radius, assuming the "L" pose with the left hand. The field mesh has a glowing and refraction shader attached to it.

As soon as the "L" pose is released, all the spheres inside the field are attracted towards the right hand, triggering collisions and changing the spatial scattering of the units. Similarly, moving the left hand in a "V" pose, with index and middle finger stretched, the user can create a red field which makes all the spheres within its radius rigidly move together with the user's right hand (Figure 5). Raising the closed fist over the head, it is possible to reset the positions of the units according to the three sound descriptors linked to (x, y, z) . This is useful when, due to collisions, spheres assume a chaotic disposition difficult to be explored.

Figure 5. In this picture a user is moving a cluster of spheres using rigid motion interaction modality. Only the spheres inside the red field are affected.

5. USER EXPERIENCE

A preliminary evaluation of the user experience inside *vrGrains* has been done. Five volunteers - three musicians among them - have been allowed to enter our department VR room to test the installation, leaving comments and suggestions. In that occasion, we connected two microphones for real-time audio stream recording and analysis through CataRT; we invited the participants to bring their own instruments and/or to speak and sing into the microphones to populate the installation with very personal samples. To this end, a small recording area has been equipped next to the interaction area of the installation. Additionally, we made available an extremely heterogeneous set of loops and samples, ranging from synthetic electro-beats to guitar and piano recordings. A brief VR training has been performed by the participants, focusing on stereoscopic perception and virtual interaction. Then, they have been left free to explore the installation, arbitrarily choosing samples and descriptors.

We encountered two different main approaches to the installation. The two participants who were musically unskilled adopted what we might define a “chaotic” approach. They preferred to explore audio units on the basis of their physical behavior, rather than according to their sonic content. Both the participants stated that they enjoyed the possibility to move and scatter a visual representation of sound over a 3D space, an uncommon experience for our senses, considering the generated audio as a consequence of the desired disposition. These users frequently recalled the interaction modalities included into the installation to randomize the units, playing with the sonic outcome of collisions. On the contrary, the three musicians showed a much more sound-oriented approach. They exploited the interaction modalities to create subspaces in which navigation produced a meaningful audio output. Their exploration was characterized by an initial rearrangement of the units, followed by a continuous and controlled sound generation. They also tried to limit triggering and collisions inside a selected part of the space.

The musically unskilled participants showed mere enthu-

siasm towards the installation. The level of control over units available through the interaction modalities seemed well suited to their explorative approach. The three musicians made, instead, important observations which reflect the aim of the installation and the potentialities of the involved technology. Although they considered the immersive audio/visual experience proposed by *vrGrains* extremely engaging, they suggested that the modification of the control paradigm could lead to the creation of a useful CBCS virtual instrument. In particular, they pushed for the implementation of a new work where collision-based triggering is not present, and where additional interaction modalities could further exploit unit mobility within the extended descriptor space, to enhance control and expression.

As expected, none of the volunteers complained about the use of markers. Indeed, they appreciated the possibility to control and interact with the environment directly with their hands, without wearing heavy or wired devices. A quick explanation of the user interface was sufficient to allow them to freely and arbitrarily rearrange audio units.

6. DISCUSSION

Most interactive features introduced in *vrGrains* extend the CataRT interface in terms of usability and control. As witnessed by the volunteers who tested the installation, this extension has a double purpose. The first purpose consists of proposing solutions for navigation inside uneven scattered corpora, thus enhancing musical expression; this refers in particular to the concept of extended descriptor space and to interaction modalities, like rigid motion, that permit to move the position in space of the spheres. On the other hand, this particular user interface has been created for an audio/visual interactive installation, rather than for a virtual instrument. Therefore, the second purpose is linked to the user’s perception of the physical and sonic space. The introduction of collision sound triggering, or the possibility to freely rearrange units scattering into chaos, make *vrGrains* an extremely reactive and unpredictable environment. Aspect and behavior of the units changes during exploration, offering each user a different personal experience. These features are suitable for a continuous and engaging discovery of the installation, though they decrease the level of control over sound synthesis.

Thanks to the current VR setup, the installation provides the user with control over conventional and unconventional physics-based behaviors. The use of stereoscopic projections rather than head mounted displays supports hybrid interactions, where the hands of the user are capable of direct control over a virtual environment that is coherently superimposed to the real world. From this perspective, the user’s body is not limited just to interaction with the installation, but becomes a physical part of it. Force fields and lights generated through combinations of hand poses spring directly from the user’s limbs, to affect sound, visual and space domain. These interactions give real-time control over the parameters that regulate the physical behavior of the environment, generating realistic (e.g., collisions) or unnatural (e.g., orbiting objects) behaviors.

7. CONCLUSION

Based on previously addressed approaches and issues, we developed *vrGrains*, an immersive VR installation which introduces new techniques for CBCS corpus navigation through means of natural interaction. The platform, relying on CataRT for sound synthesis, generates a virtual environment populated by sound units representing a corpus of choice. While the sound unit sonic features remain unchanged, their position inside the descriptor space can be modified through conventional and unconventional physics-based behaviors. The user is allowed to interact with the environment at different levels, from simple sound unit triggering to reversible chaotic rearrangement of the whole unit data. This non-destructive customization of the unit spatial distribution enhances navigation within sparse multi-dimensional descriptor spaces. The distance between sound clusters can be narrowed down by moving the clusters towards one other, making it easier to explore heterogeneous soundscapes. Although implemented within an interactive installation, we believe that the presented solution could have strong applications in purely musical contexts, as suggested by the comments of the first volunteers who tested *vrGrains*.

8. FUTURE WORK

Future work includes the assessing of different aspects and features of the installation, and of the concept of extended descriptor space as well. We would like to improve navigation and expression, introducing the possibility to arrange dynamic sub-spaces. This implicates the definition of new interaction modalities to outline different portions of the virtual environment where units can be ordered according to arbitrary sound descriptors, chosen in real-time. In this way, the concept of descriptor space would be further extended. Then, a future series of experiments will be planned in order to study in both a qualitative and quantitative way the reactions of users interacting with the installation, according to their personal approach to exploration.

The interest towards Hybrid Reality performances [15] suggests us a further future objective. The concept of extended descriptor space could be exploited in such performances showcasing interactive audio/visual choreographies for real-time CBCS. On stage, performers would be allowed to generate and explore their own live corpora through gestures and interaction paradigms similar to the ones already described for *vrGrains*.

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